

Household Floor Sample Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	Sample Type	Boot sock Swab
6	Where was it collected from?	Inside house Outside house Both inside and outside house
<i>You have completed data collection for this sample</i>		
7	Staff signature	
8	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY